

How to run a successful stakeholder meeting

Problem

In agrobiodiversity and conservation projects, meetings with stakeholders often fall short due to unclear objectives, poor preparation, or lack of trust-building. This limits meaningful collaboration and long-term engagement.

Solution

A simple, step-by-step approach to organise effective stakeholder meetings – from preparation to follow-up – helps project partners engage stakeholders meaningfully without needing event management experience.

Benefits

Improves trust and dialogue, leads to better alignment of project goals with stakeholder needs, and fosters collaborative relationships that support sustainable project outcomes.

Step-by-step guide for researchers and facilitators

1. Define your meeting goal

Determine whether the meeting is intended for information sharing, decision-making, or relationship building. Decide whether it should be face-to-face or online, depending on your objectives, the participants' locations and the type of interaction you want to encourage.

2. Identify and invite the right people

Include stakeholders relevant to your goal – farmers, policymakers, breeders, seed buyers and vendors, etc. Tailor the meeting to their background and interests. Send clear invitations early and follow up personally with key participants. For online meetings, include the meeting link, time zone and brief technical instructions.

Applicability box

Theme: Stakeholder Engagement, Project Implementation, Knowledge Exchange

Keywords: CWR, facilitation, stakeholder meeting, engagement, trust-building

Context: Diverse geographical and institutional contexts where direct stakeholder interaction is needed

Application time: Year-round; plan around local calendars and peak seasons for optimal participation

Required time: Planning: 2–4 weeks; Meeting: 0.5–2 days; Follow-up: 1–2 days

Period of impact: Short-term (immediate engagement) and long-term (relationship building)

Best in: Collaborative research projects involving farmers, researchers, policymakers, and seed sector actors

Picture 1: Stakeholder meeting in progress.

3. Choose a neutral and accessible venue

Find a comfortable and inclusive space that feels safe and accessible to everyone. For in-person meetings, provide food and informal time (e.g., over coffee) – that’s where trust is built! For online meetings, choose a user-friendly platform. Test all features the day before and always have a co-host to manage the technology and chat.

4. Create a simple, clear agenda

Balance structured content with time for interaction and discussion. Plan in space for participants to speak, question, and connect. For online meetings, define how you’ll keep engagement high (e.g., polls, breakout rooms, or interactive tools like Mentimeter or Miro). Don’t forget - breaks matter!

5. Facilitate inclusively

Welcome participants personally, explain the meeting goals, and encourage contributions from everyone. Use icebreakers and open questions. Encourage balanced participation — give quieter voices space and prevent one person from dominating. Stay flexible and adapt to the group’s energy or needs.

6. Manage time and engagement

Manage time efficiently by starting and ending on schedule, keeping discussions focused and maintaining participant engagement. Encourage interaction and balance structure with flexibility.

7. Document and follow up

Send a short thank-you message, including meeting outcomes and any agreed-upon next steps. Keep the relationship going with regular updates or invitations.

Tips and tricks

- Think "experience" – make it welcoming and meaningful
- Listen actively and with curiosity
- Tailor the content to your audience – avoid jargon
- Keep the energy human, not too formal
- Respect people’s time – prepare, start, and end on time
- Use interactivity (polls, whiteboards, questions) to sustain focus online
- Seek win-win situations and follow up with appreciation

Further reading and helpful resources

- How to organise a Face-to-Face Meeting: An easy guide: <https://zenodo.org/records/17295935>
- How to organise an Online Meeting: An easy guide: <https://zenodo.org/records/17296053>

About this practice abstract and PRO-WILD

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PRO-WILD: The project 'Protect and Promote Crop Wild Relatives - PRO-WILD' is running from September 2024 to August 2029. The overall goal of PRO-WILD is to protect and promote crop wild relatives (CWRs) to enhance the resilience of agriculture to climate change and other environmental and anthropogenic stresses. The project focuses particularly on wild relatives of wheat, sugar beet, and brassicas. It aims to strengthen both *in-situ* and *ex-situ* conservation, identify valuable genetic traits, and facilitate the use of these resources in breeding programs for future-proof agriculture.

Project website: www.pro-wild.eu

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